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Abstract	This report details the planning and execution of the second round of the ACTION Accelerator (2021). The document is intended both as documentation of the second round and as a useful resource for those considering embarking upon such an Accelerator format for the incubation of citizen science projects in general.
Keywords	Citizen science, Accelerator model, Mentoring, Co-design, participatory research

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Accelerating Citizen Science projects: Lessons from the Second Run

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report reviews the execution and outcomes of the first round of the ACTION Accelerator. Details of the Open Call (described in D3.4). It is intended to be of use to ACTION consortium, researchers and practitioners working with the Accelerator model, and those with an interest in running citizen science projects.

In this report we discuss the first round of the ACTION Accelerator from March 2021 to September 2021. We explain the methods and results of the Accelerator, such as the use of mentoring as a means to support citizen science projects, the development of webinars and regular calls, the progress of the projects through the accelerator.

1 Introduction

How can we help citizen science projects become more participatory, rigorous and inclusive? The ACTION Accelerator replies to this challenge with an intensive support programme, providing citizen science projects access to expertise and training in engagement, data science, inclusion and participation. All projects are supported by a mentor. In addition they become part of a network of practice in participatory research, are provided with bespoke consultancy and participate in peer-to-peer learning.

The ACTION Accelerator methodology has been developed in response to working closely with ACTION's citizen science projects, both those recruited through an open call, and with case study projects who have been with us from the beginning. We have refined and promoted the adoption of best practice in participatory research.

With our focus on projects related to pollution, the ACTION Accelerator has been researching how best to support projects addressing some of the most pressing challenges of Citizen Science today. The review of the First Round of the Call can be found in D2.12.

The Accelerator period ran from March - August 2021. We selected 5 projects for the ACTION Accelerator through a second open call running 1st September to 1st November 2020 (D3.4). A total of 10 projects have been funded through the Open Call. Given the ongoing uncertainty for event organisation and in-person meetings in Europe due to the COVID-19 pandemic, the Second Round of the ACTION Accelerator was planned to be delivered online only, and the Accelerator projects were required to have a significant online component to their proposal.

2 Accelerator Projects in the Second Round

Two projects from Round One had been extended to join Round Two, due to the impact of the pandemic on their possibility of realisation. These were WOWNature and Water for Future. WOWNature continued to take steps in the realisation of their Italy-based project through the winter of 2020, and were able to re-join the Accelerator on an adjusted timeline when we recommenced in 2021. However, during the negotiations phase of the recruitment of the projects 2020-2021, it became apparent that there were continued obstacles to the delivery of the completely postponed Water for Future, due to the necessity of their travelling to Peru to deliver the project. After substantial discussions, it was concluded that the proposed plans were unable to mitigate the risks to the project of continued travel restrictions, and unfortunately Water for Future left the Accelerator. We therefore recruited a fifth project from the Open Call.

Our Round Two projects were:

- 1 Walk Up Aniene (Italy): Exploring the biodiversity of the Aniene River in Rome using online training and in-person events.

- 2 Mapping Mobility (UK): App-based collaborative mapping of sustainable transport with online training in GIS.
- 3 Water Sentinals (Portugal): Community monitoring of water quality and collection of historical data around pollution events affecting seagrass meadows.
- 4 Restart Data Workbench (UK): Collective data collection and LCA calculation of the effect on carbon emissions of electronic repair using online platforms and microtasking.
- 5 Open Soil Atlas (Germany): Collaborative mapping of soil quality using DIY science methods, online training and in-person events.
- 6 WOW Nature (Italy): A project exploring and enabling the mitigation of air pollution through tree planting and urban forests in the Po Valley in Italy. They worked with community stewards of the forests to install the sensors provided by commercial partner Wiseair, who analyse the data.

3 Preparations for the Second Round

Learning from the successful delivery of the First Round of the Accelerator (D2.12) was carried forward into the preparation for the Second Round. Specifically, further attention was paid to the orientation of both the consortium and the projects to the mutual benefit of their collaboration. A consortium expertise index was created, and incoming projects were asked to create a short introductory video in advance of the kick-off meeting so that the consortium could get to know them. Furthermore, the Accelerator timeline was established well in advance, with the consortium partners coordinating dates for contact and requests for content from the projects, for a clearer and more coordinated communication between ACTION as a whole and the project teams.

In a significant change from Round One, the kick-off meeting was included in the negotiations phase of the projects' onboarding, to optimise the benefit to the project planning of the training and discussion during the workshops.

In response to feedback from Round 1, a specific training on sustainability was planned, and special attention was paid to providing a coherent overview of the activities and expertise of all of the consortium partners, including gathering in advance all interactions with and requests of the projects expected from the consortium.

4 Mentoring

A central pillar of the ACTION Accelerator is the mentoring programme. Mentors are the first point of contact for an Accelerator project during their involvement with ACTION. Mentors help projects by:

- Agreeing a workplan, including deliverables and KPIs
- Helping to bring them on board and to navigate the requirements of being involved in a project like ACTION

- Helping to determine the project needs and aims
- Liaising with IGB and other consortium partners to determine best how meeting project needs can be supported by ACTION
- Feeding back to ACTION consortium partners to open up opportunities for input into ACTION ie: into WPs 4, 5 and 6
- Ensuring that projects meet requirements set out by ACTION and the grant agreement

4.1 Assignment of Mentors

Members of the ACTION consortium were asked to volunteer in November 2020 to mentor incoming projects for the first round. The volunteers detailed their expertise and any extra notes of relevance.

The incoming projects' expected needs were assessed in the first instance through their application. Statements throughout the application were used to ascertain each project's central premise, their expected participants, the project phase, location, explicitly stated requirements, aims and methods.

One mentor was matched to each project according to a “best fit” between the expertise of the mentor and the requirements of the project. Mentors were assigned in December.

4.2 Mentor Preparation

Mentors were supplied with an updated Mentor Briefing Document (Appendix 1) and Mentoring Timeline prior to their first contact with their projects. The Mentoring Briefing Document provides the mentors with orientation on their responsibilities, along with advice on mentoring, how to support their projects, reporting requirements and how the Accelerator projects relate to the other ACTION WP2.

4.3 Mentor-Project Contact

Mentors were introduced to their projects during the negotiation phase, during which time they collaborated on the preparation of the Project Plan, including setting deliverables and milestones, and the Budget.

The main contact between the mentors and the projects is structured between the kick-off meeting and the final review by regular Interim Update group calls between all Round Two projects and mentors.

Beyond this structure, some projects were in contact with their mentor very frequently, all were in contact at least once a month. Most contact was by email, with some interaction via video or audio calls. Mentors and projects sometimes interacted via shared document editing.

4.4 Mentor-Mentor Contact

A Google Group for the Round 2 Mentors was established. This was used for mentor-mentor contact, for distribution of details about the Accelerator in general and for mentors to keep in touch with each other. Mentors were also assembled for a training meeting prior to their first contact with the project, and assembled for a catch-up mid-way through the Accelerator.

4 Workshops and Consultancy

4.1 Accelerator Kick-Off Workshop

A full description of the second Accelerator Kick-off Workshop will be provided in D2.15: Workshop Report 2. The second Accelerator Kick-off Workshop was implemented during the negotiations phase of Round 2, so that projects could implement the outcomes of this intensive training into their project plans. The workshop was designed around the Accelerator projects' requirements and aims, elicited from their application documents and the first drafts of their Project Plans. As such, the workshop oriented around a series of participatory sessions that addressed these needs.

4.2 Webinars

A series of webinars was planned in response to the requirements of the projects and in dynamic response to COVID-19. Since July, these have also allowed for networking after the presentations. These have been:

- Data Management Plan (17th March 2021)
- Data Visualisation (9th June 2021)
- Sustainability (14th July 2021)

Every webinar is recorded and put online and listed on the Accelerator page of the ACTION website.

4.3 Diversity and Inclusion

Following sessions on diversity and inclusion at the Kick-off meeting, we established regular diversity and inclusion calls between the projects. These calls allow the projects to share how they are progressing with inclusion of various stakeholders. The calls were recorded or minuted, which documentation was only made available within the ACTION citizen science project cohort and consortium.

4.4 Bespoke Co-design Workshops and Consultancy

The ACTION consortium [was](#) available for bespoke consultancy for all Accelerator projects, usually brokered by the projects' mentor. Workshops and consultancy over the Accelerator period include:

- Preparation of the Data Management Plans for all projects
- Consultancy on writing, publicising outcomes and dissemination for WOWNature

- Consultancy on the use of Zenodo for Restart Data Workbench, Open Soil Atlas
- Consultancy on video production: Water Sentinals
- Impact Assessment consultancy for all projects
- Consultancy on designing a questionnaire for citizen scientists that is both simple and scientifically valid for Walk Up Aniene
- Consultancy on navigating financial structures
- Consultancy on further funding for Open Soil Atlas
- Consultancy on engaging policymakers for WOWNature and Open Soil Atlas
- Match-making between current and previous Accelerator projects to facilitate shared learning: Noise Maps and Water Sentinals **to share perspectives on how to navigate different stakeholders' diverse needs**
- Match-making with external experts: Open Soil Atlas and the Berlin soil science community
- Match-making between student volunteers: Open Soil Atlas, Restart Data Workbench
- Consultancy on collaborative writing tools
- Consultancy in the context of the Toolkit interviews
- Attendance of in-person events: Open Soil Atlas
- Consultancy on the use of Grafana: Open Soil Atlas
- Data Quality Assessment calls with all projects plus extra consultancy
- Consultancy on Motivation with all projects
- Consultancy on various aspects of data: Walk Up Aniene

Support provided to Round 1 Projects:

- Moderation of New European Bauhaus discussion for In My Backyard (Round 1 pilot) after a screening of their documentary

5 Networking

An important aspect of the Accelerator is networking between projects, both those recruited by the open call and those with us for the entire duration of ACTION. Online networking events were planned as part of the Kick-off Meeting, including presentations and screenings by Round One projects, and were highly valued by the participants. Following feedback from Round One projects and Mentors, the written Interim Updates were replaced by monthly Interim Update Calls in which the projects presented their progress and discussed challenges they were facing within the group. These calls were open to all projects and mentors, though in practice mainly Round Two projects and their mentors attended. Regular webinars and diversity and inclusion calls provided a further opportunities through which the projects could keep in touch and share feedback.

An opt-in ACTION mailing list, set up in Round One on the UPM servers to allow projects to share interesting content with other projects, was also available to the Round Two projects but was infrequently used, with projects rather keeping in touch on an ad-hoc basis outside of the regular meetings.

5.1 Networking Outcomes

Though no concrete further plans have been made, contacts within Round 2 projects and with

Round 1 projects have been established along thematic and practice-based lines, with the intention of leveraging these relationships as and when the opportunity arises. Furthermore, network links were made between mentors / consortium partners and projects with concrete ongoing plans to work together.

7 Final Reviews

The Final Reviews were held on the 6th and the 17th -September 2021, online. The review panel consisted of two consortium members, the project mentor and Kat Austen as chair. At the start of the accelerator, the projects were supplied with a presentation template, which they used to give a 15 minute presentation providing an overview of their progress through the accelerator. Additionally, they provided their final report and video alongside their bespoke deliverables as outlined in their project plan. Reviewers were provided with a list of questions to form the basis of their evaluation of the projects (see D2.12 Appendix 3).

Presentations were followed by questions from the review panel that encompass the presentation and submitted materials. Each project graduated, and were subsequently provided with a feedback document summarising the comments from reviewers during the interviews and reviewer reports.

1. Walk Up Aniene (Italy)

The project succeeded in developing innovative methods for collecting detailed and scientifically relevant data about biodiversity along the Aniene River that would otherwise be difficult to obtain. This data can be of use to the project team as well as to scientists and policymakers. The project team have engaged with diverse stakeholders and the impact of the research is increased by the team's engagement with the River Contract negotiations. Despite timing and weather challenges, the project nevertheless successfully gathered a dataset that will be useful in addressing the issue of biodiversity along the river basin and engaged committed citizen scientists in the process.

2. Mapping Mobility (UK):

Mapping Mobility has begun to gather data on sustainable mobility through the Accelerator period and has generated training materials on citizen engagement with GIS mapping. The team designed a three-tiered participant engagement plan, with community financial incentives. Nevertheless, the project has struggled with participant engagement. Participation on the part of the community was delayed due to a lengthy university ethics approval process. As the project will continue beyond the Accelerator period, there is nevertheless an opportunity to build on existing links with the community and work with them to find ways to make the project methods fit into their daily lives.

3. Water Sentinals (Portugal)

Water Sentinals approached data collection about water pollution events with an inspiring and innovative approach of marrying historical data and water sampling by citizens combined with laboratory testing of the samples. The project team engaged with groups underrepresented in

citizen science, who participated in the data collection. Furthermore, the team engaged with diverse wider stakeholders, including potential polluters. The review panel was overwhelmingly positive in their reviews, with a particular focus on the responsible and inclusive engagement of citizens in the project.

4. Restart Data Workbench (UK)

The project achieved innovation not only in their approaches to the work – including the microtasking and types of data collected – as well as in their interaction with policy. Furthermore, the project has established a method of creating, and created, a LCA for the carbon footprint of consumer goods – knowledge that was not previously in the public realm, alongside data on common faults in these goods. The review panel commended the open source and open access commitment of the project team, including their publication of the software used.

5. Open Soil Atlas (Germany)

The project succeeded in developing a strong network around their citizen science activities and delivered an impressive amount of engagement and activities, alongside setting up a complete online set of tools to allow citizens to independently carry out soil quality assessments. There was a steep learning curve in terms of administration for the project, but this was matched by the innovative sociocratic organisational structure which also offered a learning opportunity for ACTION.

6. WOW Nature (Italy)

WOWNature joined in Round 1 of the Accelerator and continued to deliver activities – although altered in scope – between both rounds as well as during despite sometimes very challenging circumstances. The project succeeded in achieving scientifically meaningful results on the effect of trees on air pollution. However, the citizen involvement in the project was fairly limited, with the main focus being their help in data collection. Nevertheless, the project engaged with diverse stakeholders and has significant potential for impact on policy, particularly given the project's synergy with other activities by the managing organisation, Etifor.

8 Feedback and Observations

Overall, the Accelerator received a great deal of positive feedback from the projects both through feedback forms and in the projects' final reports. For instance, in their final report, Walk Up Aniene noted **in their feedback form** that being part of the Accelerator was empowering, and that the initial kick-off meeting, including training on crucial points, increased their capacity for citizen science. In general, the projects reported that the structure of engaging with the Accelerator, such as preparing a formalised and reviewed project plan at the outset, was beneficial to the organisation and efficiency of the project. Furthermore, infrastructural support provided by ACTION, such as the

web presence and templates, were helpful in getting the projects off the ground quickly. In their feedback, many projects commended the accessibility and helpfulness of the ACTION consortium.

8.1 Feedback from Mentors

Mentors reported that by engaging in the process they had greater understanding of how the projects were progressing and how their work might intersect with consortium research focusses. They also reported that the experience of mentoring fed back into their own methods of running projects.

While all mentors described the training provided to projects as comprehensive, in some cases the mentors were asked administrative questions by the pilots that could have been avoided with additional administrative / project management training. Risk assessment was also highlighted as a helpful training for projects, to support the risk assessment required in the project plan materials.

Suggestions:

- To align milestones and deliverables with milestones within the Accelerators
- To list all ACTION interactions in the project plan template as well as the timeline

8.2 Feedback from Pilots

8.2.1 Timeframe

Two projects found 6 months too short for some projects, suggest 8-10 months

Timing not optimal for many projects (and consortium partners) due to coincidence with summer holiday periods

From observation, it is clear that 6 months is very short for piloting a citizen science project, even with the support of the Accelerator, particularly if recruitment is starting from scratch.

8.2.2 Mentoring

Mentoring was found to be very important, and the mentor role as the central touchstone for each project was fundamental to orienting the projects around the consortium. For some projects this was the most important aspect of the Accelerator.

8.2.3 Kick-off

“The kick-off webinar was a very useful moment, full of interdisciplinary input to have a holistic idea of how to shape the single activities.”

8.2.4 Participation and Communities

Project reported benefitting from training and peer learning in stakeholder analysis, diversity and inclusion and engagement with policymakers. Further, training in informed consent and anonymisation materially impacted the safeguarding of citizen scientists in one project. EDI (Equity, Diversity and Inclusion) training had an impact on all projects, including in some cases running extra events to reach outside of the “usual suspects” of citizen science.

“We recruited six citizen scientists by reaching out to our community and approaching individuals

and organisations we thought might be interested. This targeted approach was suggested to us in the first ACTION inclusion and diversity call, and helped us put together a team that included a broad range of people, some with an established interest in this work (such as a Masters student), others were entirely new to the topic. While we had some interest on most channels, we quickly found that the six people who committed fully all found out about this work through our community forum. ” Upstream Report

8.2.5 Data

Projects found support in handling data crucial. From the DMP (Data Management Plan) preparation and data collection through Epicollect, through to how to publish and visualise data, guidance from the ACTION consortium had tangible effects on the outcomes of the Accelerator projects. Projects reported that the preparation of a formal DMP helped to crystallise their practices, and that in general what they had learned through the Accelerator would be used in future projects.

“...traditionally we have relied on interested parties finding our data through our own platforms and websites; we hadn’t previously considered the possibility of using Digital Object Identifiers (DOI) to share our data more widely and in this more universal way. We are now considering ways to use our datasets as a form of outreach to more specialised audiences. ” [UpstreamRestart Data Workbench](#), Final Report

“These graphs were designed after—and inspired by—attending ACTION’s Data visualisation webinar. The reminder to tell a story with data viz [visualisation] was very timely!” Restart Data Workbench, Final Report

8.2.6 Interim Meetings

The interim meetings were reported as being important to share insights and challenges with other projects and to allow for peer learning and brainstorming of solutions to specific issues the projects were facing. Joint problem solving helped to develop relationships between the cohort.

8.3 Further training

It became apparent through the course of Round 2 of the Accelerator that the following types of structured support would be beneficial to include, were the Accelerator to be repeated:

- On-boarding support for projects were engaging with European funding for the first time. This should take the form of a webinar or training session during the kick-off meeting, followed by specific financial reporting mentoring where necessary. It is clear that the impulse for this must come from within the Accelerator.
- Training in scientific framing and experimental methods. This was planned for the kick-off meeting but was cancelled at short notice due to personal circumstances. The requisite training was delivered to projects in particular need, and was reported as fundamental to the project. As such, it is likely that a global overview would have been of benefit to all projects.
- Organisational structures: at the request of the projects, a webinar on running a citizen science project as a sociocracy will be given in November.
- It was suggested that a one-to-one training to develop a sustainability / business plan would be helpful for the projects, including support for engaging further with EU funding

- frameworks.
- Were more time and capacity available, it would be beneficial to have more facilitated networking sessions between the projects that focus on their work more broadly, outside of the projects they ran as part of the Accelerator.
 - One project asked for training with UX and platform design
 - Training on the proper use of social media and digital platforms for recruitment and maintenance of online communities.
 - Risk assessment
 - Specific training in project management for both projects and mentors – this would be particularly helpful to bridge the gap in understanding between projects working on a small-medium scale and consortium partners operating within large organisations.

8.4 Testimonials

Water Sentinals “The accelerator was an excellent opportunity for our team to learn, and to share our project challenges with a multidisciplinary team of experts and others pilots. Thank you for the opportunity to grow with you.”

Restart Data Workbench “Joining the ACTION accelerator really helped us scale up our citizen science activities, allowing us to engage more of our community in new ways.”

Mentor A: “Being a mentor in other fields of research in pollution has been a quite rewarding experience. I have followed with great interest the progress of my mentored project and saw first hand non technical issues like privacy issues related to the project that I have never experienced before. My contact person was a very capable manager and we maintained a fluid relationship and identified together the critical paths, clarified issues and suggested alternative. The overall idea form me was always being there to help, not to review or supervise. I think they appreciated it very much.”

Mentor B: “The pilots were a nice experience to see what people need to start a citizen science project. These are both things they are aware of, such as an experimental setup, as things where they might not be aware of, such as data management plans and ideas on inclusivity.”

Mentor C: “It has been a lovely experience to learn how other teams work.”

8.5 Materials provided in Round 2

8.5.1 Materials for Projects

Materials provided to Round 2 projects at the beginning of the Accelerator:

8.5.1.1 Welcome Pack 2021

- Timeline
- Accelerator Documents - Folder
- Mentoring Overview
- Assessment and Support Template
- Project Plan Template
- Budget Template
- Kick-off Meeting logistical information
- Kick-off Meeting Agenda
- ACTION overview, including reporting, feedback and impact assessment tasks
- Interim Update Template
- Nextcloud login
- Nextcloud folder and file structure

8.5.1.2 Accelerator Finish

- Accelerator Feedback Questionnaire
- Final Review Presentation template
- Final Review Structure document
- Cost Statement template

8.5.2 Materials for Mentors

Mentors will be provided with access to the materials provided to the projects, and in addition the following information and meetings:

8.5.2.1 Mentor Briefing

- Updated Mentor Briefing Document
- Mentor-onboarding meeting early December
- Updated Mentor Timeline with additional Mentor Group Meetings
- Consortium Expertise Index
- Mentoring FAQs

8.5.1.2 Accelerator Finish

- Mentor Feedback Questionnaire

Appendix 1

Mentor Briefing Document

Mentor Briefing Document

If you have any queries, first see Round 2 [Mentoring FAQs](#) in case we've addressed them already.

If you are a mentor you are part of the [Mentoring Google Group Round 2](#).

!! Reminder: copy in negotiations@actionproject.eu in all emails to your projects until negotiations are completed. Please reiterate to your projects that we need them to do this. !!

Key dates

(see more detail in [Round 2 Mentoring Timeline](#))

By 11th December 2020 Mentors Assigned, first contact with project (Kat will send pairing email to projects)

11-15th January 2021 Kick-Off meeting online. Please reserve this week for the Kick-off Meeting. The agenda will be sent out at the start of January. Do you have suggestions for the Kick-Off meeting? Add them in the [Kick-Off meeting sessions list](#).

5th February 2021 The final version of your pilot's Project Plan should be approved by you.

1st March 2021 Accelerator Period begins.

27th August 2021 Project's final deliverables should be filed.

Week 6th September 2021 Final Review at which you will be part of the review panel. 1h per project.

Responsibilities

As a project mentor, you are the **first point of contact** for your Accelerator project for their involvement with ACTION. You will be helping them by:

- Agreeing a workplan including deliverables and KPIs
 - Deliverables must include a video and report at the end of the pilot; note that the production of the video may have to be budgeted!
- Being part of the Kick-Off meeting
- Helping to bring them on board and to navigate the requirements of being involved in a project like ACTION

- Helping to determine the project needs and aims
- Liaising with IGB and other consortium partners to determine best how meeting project needs can be supported by ACTION
 - Need specific expertise for your project? Check out the [ACTION Consortium Expertise Index](#) to see who to ask.
 - Missing expertise? Contact Kat at IGB to discuss options.
- **Feeding back to ACTION consortium partners to open up opportunities for input into ACTION ie: into WPs 4, 5 and 6**
- Ensuring that projects meet requirements set out by ACTION and the grant agreement if applicable

Being a good mentor

When working in support of outside partners, it's useful to bear the following in mind:

- Communication and respect are key. Your Accelerator project partners may have a very different background and expertise to you and some time should be spent getting to know each other within these parameters.
- It may be important to work at communication with care and attention to ensure mutual understanding.
- It can be useful to have set times where you will be available to give feedback to the projects, and aim for responding within a set time-frame.
- It may be that we are working with participants to the Accelerator who have significant personal investment in their projects. It is important to be aware of this if this is the case.

Things to do:

- At the start, clearly explain your role in relation to the Accelerator projects, and your role in the ACTION project as a whole.
- Let your Accelerator project explain their work to you, explore the project with Active Listening.
- Identify needs and work with your Accelerator project to set achievable aims
- Set a schedule for the next 6 months.
- Establish boundaries (eg: in terms of communication channels, response times, roles) if necessary to ensure your own resources aren't drained.

Supporting your project meet its goals

In order to help our Accelerator projects, we want to identify needs and set aims with flexibility and thoughtfulness.

- [Needs Assessment and Support Template](#)
- Set realistic aims for what could be achieved over the 6 months
- Identify opportunities for Feedback into ACTION

- Create a plan for support and contact those consortium members who can help provide it.
- If we have missing expertise raise this with Kat.

Measuring success

- Work together to develop project-specific measures of success.
- T6ECO will be working with your project to assess Impact (contact is Antonella)

Relationship with other ACTION WPs

- WP2 pilots are instrumental in the shaping of the services offered by WP4 and 5: Digital Infrastructure for Citizen Science (UPM) and Sociotechnical Citizen Science Toolkit (CEFRIEL), as well as being case studies for analysis and impact assessment (WP6).

Digital Infrastructure

Projects have a Folder set up for them where they will store all their files on the Nextcloud to which you have access along with some members of the wider consortium. This contains the sub-folders:

- Contracts - this folder should contain all the documents for a complete contract
- Deliverables - this folder should be used to upload deliverables to share with us and the reviewers
- Interim Updates - the pilots should upload their presentations for the interim update sessions here on the day of the update presentations.
- Public folder, which projects will use for logos, photos etc.

There is also a folder [News Pilots 2021](#) where they can share their news items etc. and alert WP7 for better dissemination.

The templates for Accelerator documents can be accessed on the [Nextcloud in Information for Pilots 2021> Templates folder](#).

Reporting for WP2

Reporting for WP2 is as light as possible while ensuring that projects stay on track and make the most of the short time they are with ACTION.

- Project Plan, Budget and Needs Assessment should be completed by the start of the Accelerator on 1st March 2021.
- Projects and mentors will come together for four interim update sessions. Projects will provide a short presentation in which they identify progress and challenges, and the

group discusses to help overcome challenges. A template for the presentations will be agreed in due course and you should check that the projects have uploaded their presentations by the date of the Interim Update meeting.

- Agreed deliverables.
- Final Presentation and Review

A complete contract includes:

- Contract (signed by representative; digital by 10th Jan; 2x hard copy by 16th Jan)
- Annex 1: Pilot plan + Budget
- Annex 2: Guide for applicants (we have this)
- Annex 3: Bank account information, signed by representative and bank
- Annex 4: Declaration of honour (submitted with application)
- Annex 5: Application form (submitted with application)
- Annex 6: Legal entity form
- Annex 7: Action GA

Pilot plan must include:

- Budget, including attendance of kick-off and conference (as a separate document)
- Milestones and KPIs
- Deliverables, including
 - Short report upon completion, outlining work done and outputs
 - Video (req for final payment; pilots may or may not be able to produce this themselves - if they are not, they need to budget it!)
 - Data management plan (what is collected, what happens with it, any data protection considerations; template on SharePoint!)
 - Ethical considerations (e.g. participant consent, volunteer data protection)

Resources and Quicklinks

[Consortium Expertise Index](#)

[Mentoring Documents Folder](#)

- 1) [Round 2 Mentoring Timeline](#)
- 2) Mentoring briefing document (this document)
- 3) [Assessment and Support Template](#)
- 4) Interim Update Presentation Template (to come)